

PROSPECTS FOR THE INTEGRATION OF QUARTZ-FELDSPAR CONCENTRATE OBTAINED FROM KAOLIN ENRICHMENT INTO CERAMIC PRODUCTION PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT. The paper examines the potential use of quartz-feldspar concentrate obtained as a result of kaolin enrichment to meet the growing demand for quartz-feldspar materials, which are essential components in the production of ceramic tiles, sanitary ceramics and other products. The research methodology includes laboratory tests of the chemical composition of kaolin enrichment waste and analysis of the possibility for obtaining marketable quartz-feldspar concentrates using flotation and electrostatic separation methods. The results showed that high-quality concentrates (possessing the necessary physical and chemical properties) that are suitable for ceramic production can be obtained by flotation of such waste. The use of such waste contributes to reducing waste volumes and ensuring a stable supply of raw materials for the ceramics industry.

Key words: kaolin beneficiation, quartz-feldspar concentrate, flotation, electromagnetic separation, construction ceramics.

Introduction

From a technological standpoint, quartz-feldspar raw material is a complex of minerals that includes quartz, feldspar, and microcline. In Ukraine, quartz-feldspar raw material is represented by various types of deposits, including pegmatite, granite, and quartzite. The largest deposits are located in the central and western parts of the country, specifically in the Kropyvnytskyi, Vinnytsia, and Zhytomyr regions. According to the Geological Service of Ukraine, as of 2019, seven deposits had been discovered, three of which were being developed. The total reserves calculated within these deposits amount to 6.85 million tons, providing significant potential. However, actual extraction of this product in the pre-war period was at the level of 30-50 thousand tons per year, which is significantly insufficient to cover industrial needs. Therefore, a significant portion of quartz-feldspar raw material was imported. Similar trends are observed now, which is especially noticeable against the backdrop of increasing demand for this type of product (Mykhailov, 2023).

The main consumers of quartz-feldspar raw materials are enterprises in the glass and ceramic industries. Specifically, quartz is primarily used in the production of high-quality glass, optical and technical glass, as well as in ceramic bodies. Feldspar is an important component in the manufacturing process of ceramic tiles, sanitary ceramics, and other products. Considering modern trends in construction and design, the demand for these materials continues to grow.

One of the main challenges restraining the extraction of quartz-feldspar raw materials is the relatively high cost of mining operations and the need for specialised equipment and extraction methods. These materials are predominantly found in hard rock formations, which are labour-intensive and energy-consuming to break down. Additionally, these deposits may be located at significant depths, leading to increased stripping ratios, or they may be situated in areas with complex mining-geological conditions, necessitating detailed geological exploration and the establishment of complex infrastructure to enable extraction (Sobolevskiy et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the technology for obtaining quartz-feldspar raw materials involves the enrichment of the initial mining mass, which includes multistage crushing, grinding, followed

by flotation and magnetic separation, allowing to achieve the necessary quality parameters of the material.

Therefore, considering the high demand for quartz-feldspar raw materials, the complexity of technological processes in its extraction and enrichment, and consequently the low level of profitability from its realisation, this study proposes to consider the possibility of obtaining it from kaolin enrichment wastes.

Theoretical part

The waste from kaolin enrichment, formed during the extraction and processing of kaolin deposits, is traditionally considered unsuitable for further use. However, due to the peculiarities of kaolin genesis and the increasing demand for quartz-feldspar raw materials, it is advisable to analyse the possibility of using these wastes for industrial purposes. Such an approach will not only contribute to reducing waste volumes but also positively impact the supply of raw materials to various industrial sectors (Hongjun et al., 2024).

The process of kaolin enrichment is typically carried out using one of two basic methods: wet and dry enrichment methods. However, the wet method remains predominant. In the vast majority of cases, this method involves separating kaolin concentrate by classifying fine-dispersed particles of kaolinite smaller than 0.056 mm from larger grains of quartz, feldspars, mica, and other minerals present in the kaolin rock, using either air or water as a medium. As a result, significant amounts of waste are generated, containing up to 60-70 % quartz and 10-20 % feldspar. These components are crucial minerals used in the production of ceramic and glass products.

An important aspect is the presence of impurities such as iron and titanium, which can affect the quality of the final product, and can be improved through flotation or magnetic separation.

The geological conditions of formation play a crucial role in the potential utilisation of kaolin enrichment wastes. Since this paper is based on the results of chemical analysis of the Yosypivka deposit, it would be pertinent to further elaborate on the main aspects of its geological structure.

The geological structure of the Yosypivka deposit includes Precambrian crystalline rocks, the weathering crust of these rocks, and Neogene and Quaternary sandy-clay deposits.

Within the deposit, the crystalline rocks do not naturally outcrop at the surface, lying beneath a layer of kaolin, and Jurassic and Cenozoic rocks.

Migmatites are widespread throughout the development area of alkaline kaolin deposits, containing small bodies of pegmatoid granites and pegmatites. Garnet-muscovite migmatites have a hypidiomorphic granular structure with the following mineral composition: quartz 10-15 %, plagioclase 55-58 %, microcline 15-20 %, muscovite 8-12 %, garnet 3-4 %, sericite up to 3 %.

Granites are found in the northern and southwestern parts of the deposit. Under the microscope, they exhibit a hypidiomorphic granular structure with elements of superimposed metasomatic alteration. Their mineral composition includes microcline 40-57 %, quartz 20-25 %, plagioclase 15-20 %, biotite 3-5 %, along with muscovite, sericite, leucosphen, and zircon.

Pegmatoid granites and pegmatites occur within the migmatite field as small irregular vein-like bodies. These coarse-grained rocks are pinkish-grey, light-grey, or grey in colour, with pegmatoid or hypidiomorphic granular structures.

The weathering crust of the crystalline rocks in the Yosypivka deposit ranges in depth from 3.0 m to 22.8 m, with thickness varying from 1 m to 23 m or more, averaging around 15 m.

In the weathering crust profile, from bottom to top, the following zones are distinguished:

- 1) Zone of disintegration and initial weathering (saprolite).
- 2) Hydrosericitic-kaolinic zone, including the deposit of alkaline kaolin.
- 3) Kaolinite zone.

The zone of disintegration in the Yosypivka deposit is characterised by good preservation and a high amount of microcline in the weathered crust of granitoids, together with stable quartz and accessories under hypergenic conditions, giving the rock a distinctive saprolitic appearance. In contrast, for the crust developed over gneisses, where relatively stable minerals are present in subordinate quantities, saprolitisation is

not characteristic; instead, there is a gradual transition from crystalline rocks to hydroxy - aluminosilicate - kaolinite formations.

The hydroxy-aluminosilicate-kaolinite zone within the deposit is widespread, characterised by a sharp predominance of secondary minerals over primary products. In this zone, the kaolinisation of plagioclase, muscovite hydration, and biotite occurs. Despite significant kaolinisation, microcline remains in substantial amounts.

The kaolinite zone (complete kaolinisation) represents the final product of chemical weathering of crystalline rocks in a humid climate. This zone contains kaolins composed of kaolinite and quartz, with other minerals present in very small quantities. In the deposit, this zone is identified at the uppermost part of the rock weathering profile (Pidvysotskyi et al., 2022).

The deposit has a fairly typical geological structure for kaolin deposits, characterised by the presence of Precambrian crystalline rocks, weathered into hydroxylation-kaolinite and kaolinite zones. These zones contain significant amounts of quartz and feldspar. Therefore, the enrichment of kaolin waste and their further use in ceramic production is a promising direction that can supply the industry with important materials, reduce waste volumes, and have a positive environmental impact.

One of the most promising directions for the use of enriched kaolin products could be their utilisation as raw materials for the ceramic industry. The requirements for raw materials suitable for ceramic production are currently outdated and defined by the provisions of GOST 7030-75, upon which a series of Technical Specifications have been developed for use within individual enterprises. The possible directions for the use and types of quartz-feldspar raw materials are specifically listed in Table 1.

Each of the specified types must meet a number of technical requirements to ensure the necessary quality of the final product.

Table 1. Directions of application of quartz-feldspar raw materials in the ceramic industry

Material	Type	Directions of application
During the production of fine ceramics		
Finely ground quartz-feldspar raw material (FGQFRM)	FGQFRM 0.2-2	To manufacture artistic and household porcelain, faience, and electrical porcelain
Ground quartz-feldspar raw material (GQFRM)	GQFRM 0.2-2	To manufacture artistic and household porcelain, faience, and electrical porcelain
	GQFRM 0.3-2	Manufacturing of electrical porcelain
Quartz-feldspar raw coarse material (QFRC)	QFRC 0.2-3; QFRC 0.2-2	To manufacture artistic and household porcelain, faience, and electrical porcelain.
	QFRC 0.3-3; QFRC 0.3-2	Manufacturing of electrical porcelain
During the manufacturing of the construction ceramics		
Quartz-feldspar raw material (QFRM)	QFRM 0.2-0.9; QFRM 0.3-0.9	Manufacturing of sanitary ceramics
	QFRM 0.2-0.5	For manufacturing decorative and cladding tiles, and low-temperature porcelain
	QFRM 0.3-0.7	For manufacturing decorative and cladding tiles

The high quality of quartz-feldspar raw material is primarily ensured by the requirements for its chemical composition. The

key components are SiO₂ (silicon dioxide) and Al₂O₃ (aluminum oxide). The content of SiO₂ should be around 60 %, which

guarantees high temperature resistance and strength of the final product. The content of Al_2O_3 should range between 15-25 %, ensuring proper fire resistance and mechanical stability. Additionally, small amounts of alkalis (Na_2O , K_2O) and iron (Fe_2O_3) are allowed, but their content should be minimised, as an excess of these elements can lead to undesirable colour changes and reduced strength of the products (Ryshchenko et al., 2008; Cely, 2016; Larsen et al., 2016).

Regarding the mineral composition, quartz and feldspar (albite or orthoclase) should predominantly occupy the mix. The presence of other minerals, such as microcline, may be acceptable but only in small quantities. Contamination with minerals such as mica, kaolinite, or hematite can negatively affect the technological properties of the ceramic body, reducing its plasticity and increasing the sintering time.

Equally important is the granulometric composition; specifically, the raw material particles must have a certain size and distribution to ensure the necessary density and uniformity of the mass.

Typically, the optimal particle size for quartz and feldspar ranges from 50 to 200 micrometers. The presence of particles that are too fine or too large can lead to defects in the structure of ceramic products, such as pores or cracks.

The technological process of ceramic manufacturing is significantly influenced by physical properties such as bulk density, moisture content, plasticity, and firing temperature.

Bulk density should be sufficiently high to ensure the necessary mechanical strength and stability. Moisture content of the raw material should be minimised to avoid undesirable chemical reactions during firing. Plasticity of the raw material should facilitate ease of shaping products and their resistance to mechanical stresses during the manufacturing process. Firing temperature should be sufficiently high to ensure complete sintering and achieve a dense, strong structure of the products. Detailed requirements for the quality indicators of quartz-feldspar raw materials of various types are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Technological requirements for the quality of quartz-feldspar raw materials used in the ceramic industry

Indicator	Fine ceramics				Construction ceramics			
	FGQFRM 0.20-3	FGQFRM 0.20-2 QFRM 0.20-2 QFR 0.20-2	QFAR 0.30-3	QFM 0.30-2 QFR 0.30-2	QFM 0.2-0.9	QFM 0.2-0.5	QFM 0.3-0.9	QFM 0.3-0.7
Mass fraction of Al_2O_3 (%), not less than	15	15	10	10	15	10	10	10
Mass fraction of Fe_2O_3 (%), not more than	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3
Mass fraction of TiO_2 (%), not more than	CNR				CNR			
Mass fraction of $CaO + MgO$ (%), not more than	1.5	2	1.5	2	2	1.5	2	2.5
Mass fraction of $K_2O + Na_2O$ (%), not less than	8	8	8	8	8	9	7	7
Ratio of K_2O to Na_2O , not less than	3	2	3	2	0.9	≤0.5	0.9	0.7
Mass fraction of quartz (%), not more than	30	30	30	30	35	30	40	40
Mass loss during firing (%), not more than	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.8
Number of mica flakes (pieces) per 100 mineral grains, not more than	CNR	2	CNR	2	CNR			
Quality of the body after firing at a temperature of 1350-1370 °C	Clean without flaws				Clean without flaws			
Mass fraction of moisture (%), not more than	CNR	1	CNR	1	2	2	2	2

* CNR - content not regulated

Methodology

To confirm the feasibility of using quartz-feldspar material formed as a result of kaolin enrichment, laboratory research was conducted with the aim of determining the chemical composition of the enrichment products (Figure 1). The enrichment products were obtained through wet enrichment of kaolin mass, which included disintegration of the raw material, coarse classification to remove granular abrasive particles, and subsequent fine classification to remove fine abrasive particles.

Laboratory research on the chemical composition of kaolin enrichment waste was carried out at the "Shpat" State

Enterprise, which is involved in the development of the Yosypivka deposit. During the study, the separation of kaolin from sand was conducted using a 0.056 mm sieve. The sand residue was studied to obtain conditioned quartz and quartz-feldspar concentrates using flotation methods in acidic and near-neutral environments, as well as electrical separation methods (Normatov et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021; Mohanty et al., 2024). Quaternary ammonium salts were used as collectors, and potassium chloride was used as a depressant for feldspars.

Fig. 1. Scheme of quartz-feldspar concentrate enrichment (kaolin enrichment waste)

Results and discussion

Flotation of sands in an acidic environment was applied as an evaluation parameter to achieve the highest possible separation indicators for feldspar and quartz.

The results showed that flotation of sands allows obtaining conditioned quartz-feldspar and quartz concentrates according to the requirements of GOST 7030-75.

Flotation of sands in a near-neutral environment (pH = 6-7) demonstrated the ability to increase the content of alkali metal oxides in enrichment products without the use of aggressive environments.

Electromagnetic separation of sands was carried out after grinding to 0.5 mm and desliming to the 0.056 mm class. A concentrate with an alkali content exceeding 8 % was obtained after primary electrostatic separation. The yield of quartz-feldspar product averaged 31.6 % of the initial mass of raw kaolin.

The results of the chemical analysis of the studied samples are presented in Table 3, which shows the concentration of their main constituent components.

According to the results, a high content of silicon dioxide is observed in the samples. This positively affects the physical and mechanical properties of ceramic products, particularly their strength and thermal resistance.

However, significant excess of SiO₂ content may require adjustments in the production of fine ceramics, where excessive quartz content can lead to increased brittleness.

Aluminum oxide, which promotes the formation of a glassy phase during ceramic firing, is characterised by moderate content, ensuring necessary fluidity and viscosity.

The low content of iron oxide is a critical factor for the production of fine ceramics, where the presence of iron can cause defects and alter the colour of products. Values exceeding 0.2 % require additional purification or processing of raw materials for use in high-quality ceramic products.

Table 3. Chemical composition of the quartz-feldspar concentrate obtained during kaolin enrichment

Sample number	Chemical composition. % (sand fraction)										Calculation of quartz content. %
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	CaO	SO ₂	MgO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O+ Na ₂ O	
1	80.77	10.14	0.21	0.06	0.1	0.06	-	7.9	0.2	8.1	39.8
2	79	10.9	0.29	0.05	0.1	0.06	-	8.76	0.24	9	34.5
3	80.38	9.99	0.22	0.06	0.1	0.06	-	8.34	0.24	8.58	37.5
4	77.81	11.41	0.25	0.11	0.1	0.06	-	9.28	0.35	9.63	30.9
5	79.05	10.81	0.29	0.08	0.1	0.06	0.19	8.34	0.35	8.69	35.8
6	79.28	10.64	0.25	0.07	0.1	0.06	0.11	8.37	0.37	8.74	35.8
7	81.77	9.26	0.27	0.07	0.1	0.06	-	7.62	0.24	7.86	41.7
8	80.3	10.05	0.28	0.07	0.1	0.06	-	8.35	0.24	8.59	37.4
9	81.45	9.25	0.34	0.07	0.1	0.06	-	7.9	0.24	8.14	40.3
10	80.34	10.37	0.23	0.07	0.1	0.06	-	7.9	0.24	8.14	39.2
11	78.54	11.24	0.34	0.12	0.1	0.06	-	8.49	0.28	8.77	35
12	78.34	11.16	0.26	0.1	0.1	0.06	-	8.92	0.28	9.2	33.1
Total	957.03	125.22	3.23	0.93	1.2	0.72	0.30	100.17	3.27	103.44	441
Avg.	79.75	10.43	0.26	0.07	0.1	0.06	0.15	8.34	0.27	8.62	36.75

The total alkali oxides meet the requirements of the ceramic industry, ensuring necessary melting characteristics and stability at high temperatures. A high ratio of K₂O to Na₂O

indicates specific properties of the raw material that may require adjustments during the manufacturing process.

The quartz content exceeds permissible limits for fine ceramics (up to 30 %), which can lead to increased fragility of products. However, this indicator is within acceptable limits for construction ceramics (up to 40 %).

Considering the constantly increasing level of globalisation, it is advisable to analyse not only potential domestic markets for quartz-feldspar raw materials obtained through kaolin enrichment, but also to align with the requirements of other countries. Particularly promising in this case are the countries of the European Union. According to current European standards, the main components of quartz-feldspar raw materials are silicon dioxide (SiO₂) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃). According to GOST 7030-75 requirements, the SiO₂ content should be around 60 %, with Al₂O₃ ranging from 10 to 15 %. European documents also impose requirements on the content of these components, ensuring high quality of the final products. For instance, SiO₂ content must be between 50 and 80 %, while Al₂O₃ should be between 8 - 30 % in materials for preparing bricks and roof tiles. These values guarantee better thermal resistance and mechanical stability of ceramic products. For household ceramics Fe₂O₃ content is limited to 0.2 %, and Na₂O+K₂O must be at least 9 %. This reduces the risk of defects and enhances the quality of finished products; excessive iron presence can lead to unwanted colour changes and decreased strength of the products (European Commission, 2023).

Equally important is the mineral composition of the raw materials. For example, European documents dictate that quartz content should not exceed 35 % for household earthenware, ensuring better homogeneity and stability of ceramic mass (European Commission, 2023). The requirement for the optimal particle size is the range from 45 - 150 micrometers.

Conclusion

Based on the conducted enrichment experiments and analysis of the obtained concentrate, it can be concluded that waste materials from kaolin enrichment in the form of quartz-feldspar raw materials have significant potential for use in ceramic production, particularly in building ceramics. High content of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ ensures necessary physicochemical properties, while low content of CaO and MgO minimises the risks of defects formation. However, some indicators, such as Fe₂O₃ content, may require additional processing or adjustment of the technological process to meet the requirements of fine ceramics.

Therefore, the utilisation of quartz-feldspar raw materials from kaolin enrichment waste is a promising direction that will contribute to waste reduction and ensure stable supply of raw materials for the ceramic industry.

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